

Analysis and machine learning on logs of the monitoring infrastructure

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AUTHOR:

Mert Ozer

SUPERVISOR:

Borja Garrido Bear

ABSTRACT

The CERN IT/monitoring team handles around 5000 gigabytes of data every day millions of monitoring events from the CERN data centers and the WLCG sites. Today this data is provided to users through a number of different tools and dashboards. This project aims at exploring with practical examples of new logging, data transport, deployment techniques and applied machine learning in order to extend the current infrastructure and also apply such techniques to IT services and the monitoring service itself.

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INTRODUCTION

The CERN Data Centre [1] is the heart of CERN's entire scientific, administrative, and computing infrastructure with 16 000 processor cores and 11 000 servers running 24/7. This computing power is extended with Wigner Data Centre with 56 000 processor cores and 3 500 servers in order to meet the increasing demands of the LHC experiments. In average, there are more than 300,000 batch jobs running every hour and, on a daily basis, terabytes of data are transferred between sites. The Monitoring team of the IT Compute and Monitoring (CM) group is responsible for providing monitoring solutions for these resources by handling millions of monitoring events from the CERN data centers and the WLCG sites on a daily basis.

Handling this huge amount of data requires constant maintenance. Therefore providing a reliable monitoring service is extremely important for an efficient use of the CERN data centres and the WLCG sites.

The goal of this project is to make use of the logs coming from different services in order to better understand and improve some monitoring service components. To achieve that, logs are sent to the Monitoring service so that they are stored in a central place, furtherly this allowed us to develop some typical monitoring displays, such as general information about services overviews, creating service-specific dashboards of data extracted from the logs and finally apply a machine learning approach to detect anomalies in such services.

The first part of the report consists of an overview of the technologies that were used to ingest the data inside the monitoring infrastructure, including the transformation into a structured schema for easy analysis.

The second part of this report is related to the analysis performance over the data by using various techniques such as visual analysis on plots and machine learning algorithms. During this project, machine learning is used to detect advanced problems where the visualisations are not enough to understand our data behaviour. In addition, a detailed explanation of how the machine learning model was chosen, the struggle faced during the implementation phase and the results are shared in this part of the report.

Data Ingestion

Data ingestion in this project consists on the usage of two main technologies, Logstash and Puppet.

Logstash

Logstash [2] is an open source data processing pipeline that is used for parsing and transporting the data to a desirable output. It is widely used because of his support to a variety of inputs that enables pulling events from multitude of common sources at the same time to a centralized logs place.

As data travels, Logstash parses each event, identifies named fields to build a queryable data and transform them into a common structured format for easier analysis and visualizations.

Why Centralized Logs?

Logs are a critical part of any system, they are indispensable when we want to know how well the system is doing, as well as what happened or what was causing the errors. Almost every process running on a system generates logs. Usually, these logs are written to files on local disks.

On a big project with lots of hosts and users, managing the logs and accessing them gets complicated by time. Think about searching a specific error from hundreds of files with lots of lines. An easy way to tackle this problem is setting up a centralized logging so that logs can be aggregated in a central location.

Why Logstash for centralized logging?

Logstash has a rich collection of input, filter, codec and output plugins. They allow to parse unstructured log data into something structured, queryable and aggregate them in a central location. The following line is from a file which consist thousands of lines, and this file is part of one directory with multiple ones.

```
[03/Aug/2017:16:53:33 +0200] "GET /api/search?limit=10&query=&tag=wlcg HTTP/1.1" 200 211 "https://monit-grafana-dev.cern.ch/dashboard/db/default?orgId=1" "Mozilla/5.0 (X11; Linux x86_64) AppleWebKit/537.36 (KHTML, like Gecko) Chrome/60.0.3112.78 Safari/537.36"
```

With the help of the logstash plugins while the data is transferred to a central place, it is also transformed to a structured form. The following line is the structured form of the previous line.

```
metadata.type:apache
data.request:/api/search ? limit = 10 & query = & tag = wlcg
data.verb:GET
data.response:200
data.referrer:"https://monit-grafana-dev.cern.ch/dashboard/db/default?orgId=1"
data.agent:"Mozilla/5.0 (X11; Linux x86_64) AppleWebKit/537.36 (KHTML, like Gecko) Chrome/60.0.3112.78 Safari/537.36"
data.bytes:211
data.httpversion: 1.1
metadata.timestamp: [1501772013000]
```


Puppet

Puppet [3] is an open source systems management tool for centralizing and automating configuration management.

Today the CERN computer centre is a facility with more than 30,000 Puppet-managed virtual and physical nodes. Maintaining such a large infrastructure is a very demanding challenge and the need for an automated configuration management system is evident. CERN's new configuration management system provides development, support and maintenance of the range of tools and infrastructure needed to manage the configuration of any machines hosted in the CERN Computer Centre.

In this project Puppet manifest are written in order to configure virtual nodes.

Data Analysis

In the case of current project, two tools were used for analysing the data. Kibana for visualization and Apache Spark for machine learning and deeper analysis.

Kibana

Kibana [4] is an analytics and visualization platform to help its users to understand their data better. Kibana is used to quickly and easily visualize large volumes of data and its browser-based interface enables to quickly create and share dynamic dashboards that display changes to Elasticsearch queries in real time becoming these the reasons of the usage of Kibana in this project. Kibana is divided in four sections: Discover, Visualize, Dashboard and Settings and the first three are used for visual analyzation of data.

1. Discover

Discover section is used for interactively explore data. It is easy to submit search queries, filter the search results, and view documents data. It is used for understanding a feature before generating dashboards to visualize the data, since no previous knowledge of the data is needed.

2. Visualize

This section is used to design data visualizations. Visualizations will be saved and then used individually, or combined in a dashboard.

3. Dashboard

A Kibana dashboard displays a set of saved visualizations in groups that can be arranged freely. Dashboards can be shared or reloaded at a later time.

Apache Spark

Apache Spark™ [5] is a fast and general engine for large-scale data processing. Run programs up to 100x faster than Hadoop MapReduce in memory, or 10x faster on disk because of it's ability to perform “in-memory” processing.

Figure 1: Comparison of running time of Map Reduce and Spark computation paradigms.[6]

In this project Apache spark is used to read data from HDFS and apply machine learning to detect anomalies in the kafka cluster ran by the monitoring service, where specific dashboards are not enough.

What is the purpose of anomalies detection?

There is a huge possibility of getting unexpected errors after upgrading to a new compiler or switching to new version of a technology. This is why applying machine learning to our centralized data will produce the chance to catch something that cannot be seen by human eyes. In the end, we will look closer to our anomalies, find what caused them and hopefully fix them.

How the model has been selected?

We know that some events are happening in the wrong sequences in our Kafka clusters. So in order to find them we decided to apply machine learning. Several machine learning algorithms are evaluated and in the end Markov Chain rule is implemented. To understand why Markov Chain rule is selected, we should have a look at one log line from kafka cluster to get an overview of the logs.

A log line from kafka server:

```
[(kafka.log.TimeIndex),INFO,[2017-07-31 02:51:35,918] INFO Deleting index /var/spool/kafka/collectd_raw_processes-12/00000000000264011500.timeindex.deleted]
```

First field (`kafka.log.TimeIndex`) indicates the state of the log.

Second field (`INFO`) is about log level.

Third field (`2017-07-31 02:51:35,918`) is timestamp and this represents when the log line was written.

Fourth field, which is the whole log line is the raw message.

After analyzing our data, we started looking at supervised approaches to solve our problem since they have the best results [7]. Although we do not have a labeled data set nor the expertise to create one. Being this the case, a supervised learning model cannot be considered as a solution to our problem without investing a lot of effort to gain the needed knowledge over the data set.

K-NN (*k*-nearest neighbors), K-means and DBSCAN (Density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise) algorithms were also considered. Clustering our data could help finding anomalies, since an unknown anomaly will be closer to a known one or small cluster is likely to

be consist of anomalies, but since these algorithms cannot provide the information about sequence, they were dropped from the candidates.

Markov chain models help to find the probability of transition from one state to another. In this example, `kafka.log.TimeIndex` is representing the state of our model. The log line written after this line, could be only `kafka.coordinator.GroupMetadataManager` or `kafka.log.OffsetIndex`.

A simple model for our case would look like:

Figure 2: An example of Markov chain model.

Nodes: Indicates current log state name

Edges: Probability of transition to another state.

Model will be created and then for every observation, probability of being in state j after seeing the first t observed events is calculated. If there is a significant difference between two sequenced events, the last event is labeled as outlier and will be looked at closely.

This is why Markov chain model was chosen to detect anomalies in our Kafka clusters.

Implementation of the model

Our kafka logs are written in Hdfs daily. So in order to create our transition matrix, 1 week of data is read. After that, data is filtered by a specific host and ordered by timestamp value for getting consistent results. A simple visualization of transition matrix:

State/State	log.TimeIndex	log.Log	log.OffsetIndex	GroupMetadataManager	State x
log.TimeIndex	0.054	0.109	0.0727	0.0
log.Log	0.127	0.509	0.0	0.018
log.OffsetIndex	0.036	0.0363	0.0	0.0
GroupMetadataManager	0.0	0.018	0.0	0.0
State x

After having our transition matrix, for every log line we have in our data, the function in Figure 2 is executed and compared with the previous one. If there is a significant difference between the new line and previous line, new line is labeled as an outlier and will be looked closely.

```

function FORWARD(observations of len  $T$ , state-graph of len  $N$ ) returns forward-prob

  create a probability matrix  $forward[N+2, T]$ 
  for each state  $s$  from 1 to  $N$  do                                     ; initialization step
     $forward[s, 1] \leftarrow a_{0,s} * b_s(o_1)$ 
  for each time step  $t$  from 2 to  $T$  do                               ; recursion step
    for each state  $s$  from 1 to  $N$  do
       $forward[s, t] \leftarrow \sum_{s'=1}^N forward[s', t-1] * a_{s',s} * b_s(o_t)$ 

     $forward[q_F, T] \leftarrow \sum_{s=1}^N forward[s, T] * a_{s,q_F}$            ; termination step
  return  $forward[q_F, T]$ 

```

Figure 3: Forward probability pseudocode.[8]

Results

Abnormal behaviour in qa hosts

The first day we implemented this visualization, we realized that some host were producing almost 10.000 times more logs than the others. This bottleneck was slowing running jobs. Thanks to our visualization we were able to recognized the problem and detect the abnormal nodes of the

Figure 4: Normal behaviour in production phase.

This is a daily visualization of kafka clusters showing the amount of logs produced by clusters per hour. The X axis represents hours and the Y axis represents count of logs produced by clusters. We have 11 different clusters and they are all behaving in a similar way.

Figure 5: Abnormal behaviour in qa phase.

This is 24 hour visualization of kafka clusters in qa showing the amount of logs produced by clusters per hour. The horizontal axis represents hours and the vertical axis represents count of logs produced by clusters.

We have 8 different log producers in this visualization. Although, not all of them are working at the same speed. We can see only 3 different clusters doing all of the jobs.

At this point, I realized how critical to visualize the data. If I had to look all logs manually, I would have miss that only 3 clusters were working, but with this visualization I became aware of the problem within seconds.

Hourly visualization of grafana users

The purpose of this visualization is to detect slow response times based on the number of active users.

Figure 6: Hourly visualization of grafana users in qa.

The horizontal axis represents time and the vertical axis represents unique count of users.

We are going to compare this visualization with the response time visualization and we will decide if slow response time are caused by numbers of users or some unknown field is causing the slow response time.

Error tracking with other information

Figure 7: Tracking errors by time, host also syslog data for extra information.

With these visualization, now it is really simple to track all errors from multiple host together with the syslog information. Also with Kibana's intuitive interface, we can filter by any feature available in the message. An example in this regard would be clicking to one or some of the host

from the visualization and only seeing relevant syslog messages and other filtered visualization such as the raw message, error type.

Which dashboards are used more?

The result of this visualization will be used in paying more attention to the most used dashboards and also will help knowing which kind of data we are requesting from the different endpoints.

In the last stance it will also help archiving long time not used dashboards if needed.

Figure 8: Most used dashboards count.

Wrong sequenced events in kafka clusters

After creating our model and transition matrix, the forward probability function we implemented is executed for every log line in a file.

The result of our anomaly detection in a random day file:

```
line number = 12 kafka.log.Log → kafka.cluster.Partition probability = 2.87180248438e-16
```

```
line number = 14 kafka.cluster.Partition → kafka.log.Log probability = 2.9098191238e-21
```

```
line number = 16 kafka.log.Log → kafka.cluster.Partition probability = 4.08374438182e-25
```

```
line number = 19 kafka.log.OffsetIndex → kafka.cluster.Partition probability = 2.75853639275e-31
```

```
line number = 22 kafka.server.ReplicaFetcherThread → kafka.server.ReplicaFetcherThread  
probability = 3.77749216634e-40
```

- Line number indicates the line number in the current file.
- Second field, represents the state of the current line.
- Third field shows the next state of the current line.
- Fourth field is the probability of being in the current state after seeing the first t observed events.

Future work

Remember our kafka logs were looking like the following:


```
[(kafka.log.TimeIndex),INFO,[2017-07-31 02:51:35,918] INFO Deleting index
/var/spool/kafka/collectd_raw_processes-12/0000000000264011500.timeindex.deleted
(kafka.log.TimeIndex)]
```

For now, what we are modeling a Markov Chain rule in order to find wrong sequences in the clusters.

In order to get more useful information, text clustering could be done to find more anomalies in the raw message.

This was how the transition matrix was looking like after reading 1 week of data.

State/State	log.TimeIndex	log.Log	log.OffsetIndex	GroupMetadataManager	State x
log.TimeIndex	0.054	0.109	0.0727	0.0
log.Log	0.127	0.509	0.0	0.018
log.OffsetIndex	0.036	0.0363	0.0	0.0
GroupMetadataManager	0.0	0.018	0.0	0.0
State x

In order to get more accurate results, more data could be read and written to the disk.

Lastly, after being sure about the anomalies, log lines can be labeled so that later on supervised methods can be applied.

Conclusion

The Monitoring team at CERN provides tools and services that allows monitoring and understanding of the complex WLCG infrastructure and hosts running in the datacentre; thus, helps to achieve an efficient use of the system.

The goal of this project was to improve the utilization of the monitoring infrastructure at CERN, in order to improve the way the team monitored their own tools and services.

First step of the project was to import Apache, Kafka and Grafana logs to a central place using Logstash. While logs are transferred into a central place, they are also transformed into a structured form so that later on an analysis phase could take place on top of them.

The second step of the project was to visualize queryable data in order to understand and optimize monitored services by creating different plots and dashboards using Kibana. Two dashboards have been made, each one containing several visualizations. With the help of the visualizations, now it is easy to monitor and track errors in monitoring tools and services at CERN.

The last part of the project was to find wrong sequenced events in the Kafka clusters. Markov Chain model was used to detect anomalies and Spark framework was used to implement the code.

While contributing to this project, I have studied many technologies such as Logstash, Kibana, Spark framework, Hadoop, Kafka, Flume and worked in a DevOps environment.

I know that this practical experience with modern logging, transport technologies, and machine learning, will have a very positive impact to my future career. Hope to come back and contribute more. Thank you CERN!

References

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